

THE STATE OF GOAT BREEDING IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract. *The article describes the state of goat breeding in Karakalpakstan and outlines measures for its further development.*

Keywords: *goat breeding, productivity, measures for the further development of the industry.*

Introduction. Animal husbandry is an important component of Karakalpakstan agriculture, contributing to the provision of food products to the population and raw materials to industry. Its significance is especially acute due to the intensive growth of industry, the creation of new industries, and the increase in the number of residents in cities and centralized settlements.

Depending on the natural and climatic conditions of the regions, livestock farming in Karakalpakstan is divided into intensive (industrial), pasture (extensive), and domestic livestock farming. For example, dairy cattle breeding and poultry farming are concentrated in suburban irrigated areas and depend entirely on production intensity; pasture livestock breeding - goat breeding, sheep breeding, camel breeding - is based in regions with low natural resource potential, its technical cycle is mainly extensive and entirely depends on natural and fodder conditions; household livestock breeding is based on household plots, household plot products, and purchased feed.

The living standards of the population living here and their well-being depend on the state of livestock and pastures, therefore, one of the main problems of their sustainable development of the regions is ensuring the rational management of livestock and pastures in this zone. The main types of pasture livestock in the Republic are sheep and goat breeding, and the following table shows the number of sheep and goats raised by region.

Result. Analysis of the presented data shows that most of the raised small livestock is concentrated in the northern regions of the republic. A more detailed analysis showed that in the northern regions, mainly goats and fat-tailed sheep are raised, and in the southern region, Karakul sheep are raised. The proportion of goats in the total number of MRS is 69.5%.

Goat breeding is practiced everywhere, mainly local coarse-wooled goats are raised in private households and farms - goats are most adapted to the desert pastures of the northern regions, where coarse-stemmed shrubs and semi-shrubs, coarse-wormwood vegetation, and others predominate.

Table 1

Number of goats and sheep bred in Karakalpakstan (goal)

Breeding region	In all categories of farms		In farms		Dehkan farms		Agricultural enterprises					
	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %			
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1240831	1251876	100,9	187 231	188 032	100,4	1020394	1031892	101,1	33206	31 952	96,2
Districts:												
Amudarya	111172	111641	100,4	3 288	3 292	100,1	105726	105965	100,2	2 158	2 384	110,5
Beruniy	81 617	82 129	100,6	24 647	24 712	100,3	55 639	56 084	100,8	1 331	1 333	100,2
Bozataw	28 935	29 231	101,0	5 376	3 146	58,5	22 762	25 512	112,1	797	573	71,9
Kanlikul	32 430	32 541	100,3	7 066	4 557	64,5	24 560	27 161	110,6	804	823	102,4
Karauzyak	102 098	102 972	100,9	11 311	11 955	105,7	88 852	89 257	100,5	1 935	1 760	91,0
Kegeyli	35 531	35 999	101,3	3 666	3 848	105,0	30 698	30 973	100,9	1 167	1 178	100,9
Kungirot	106 840	107 013	100,2	15 779	15 781	100,0	88 688	89 390	100,8	2 373	1 842	77,6
Moynak	34 213	33 818	98,8	4 711	3 799	80,6	27 843	29 335	105,4	1 659	684	41,2
Nukus	32 055	32 119	100,2	3 354	3 356	100,1	26 455	26 515	100,2	2 246	2 248	100,1
Takhiyatash	18 311	18 803	102,7	4 144	4 342	104,8	14 080	14 374	102,1	87	87	100,0
Takhtakupir	159 244	162 051	101,8	28 055	31 564	112,5	126 924	127 123	100,2	4 265	3 364	78,9
Turtkul	171 123	173 294	101,3	38 331	39 412	102,8	124 955	124 957	100,0	7 837	8 925	113,9
Khujayli	30 966	31 365	101,3	5 107	5 119	100,2	25 226	25 576	101,4	633	670	105,8
Chimboy	64 563	64 717	100,2	7 158	6 571	91,8	56 120	56 861	101,3	1 285	1 285	100,0
Shumonay	77 883	78 939	101,4	3 965	4 526	114,1	71 430	71 730	100,4	2 488	2 683	107,8
Ellikkala	144 979	145 994	100,7	21 273	22 052	103,7	121 962	122 233	100,2	1 744	1 709	98,0
Nukus city	8 871	9 250	104,3	0	0	0,0	8 474	8 846	104,4	397	404	101,8

Table 2

Total volume of wool produced in the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Breeding region	In all categories of farms			In farms			Dehkan farms			Agricultural enterprises		
	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %	2023 y.	2024 y.	Growth %
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1 559,0	1 572,0	100,8	244,0	243,0	99,6	1 267,0	1 292,0	102,0	48,0	37,0	77,1
Districts:												
Amudaryya	86,3	86,4	100,1	9,7	6,7	69,1	61,7	70,9	114,9	14,9	8,8	59,1
Beruniy	101,4	102,5	101,1	36,2	37,2	102,8	61,0	61,1	100,2	4,2	4,2	100,0
Bozataw	20,5	20,8	101,5	5,9	4,9	83,1	14,0	15,4	110,0	0,6	0,5	83,3
Kanlikul	27,1	27,7	102,2	6,6	3,6	54,5	19,9	23,4	117,6	0,6	0,7	116,7
Karauzyak	99,3	100,2	100,9	18,2	16,9	92,9	76,3	81,9	107,3	4,8	1,4	29,2
Kegeyli	26,1	26,6	101,9	2,6	2,6	100,0	22,3	23,4	104,9	1,2	0,6	50,0
Kungirof	171,3	169,8	99,1	20,7	20,8	100,5	148,2	146,5	98,9	2,4	2,5	104,2
Moynak	29,9	30,0	100,3	4,6	3,6	78,3	24,1	25,7	106,6	1,2	0,7	58,3
Nukus	22,9	27,1	118,3	3,4	3,6	105,9	16,9	21,5	127,2	2,6	2,0	76,9
Takhiyatash	33,3	34,5	103,6	9,6	10,0	104,2	23,5	24,3	103,4	0,2	0,2	100,0
Takhtakupir	206,0	206,3	100,1	39,8	41,1	103,3	162,5	159,5	98,2	3,7	5,7	154,1
Turtkul	277,3	278,9	100,6	47,7	48,1	100,8	224,9	225,9	100,4	4,7	4,9	104,3
Khujayli	57,0	58,2	102,1	5,7	6,2	108,8	50,7	50,8	100,2	0,6	1,2	200,0
Chimboy	55,9	56,2	100,5	6,0	6,0	100,0	49,1	49,4	100,6	0,8	0,8	100,0
Shunonay	62,7	63,5	101,3	6,2	6,6	106,5	52,7	55,4	105,1	3,8	1,5	39,5
Ellikkala	272,4	273,4	100,4	21,1	25,1	119,0	249,6	247,0	99,0	1,7	1,3	76,5
Nukus city	9,6	9,9	103,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	9,6	9,9	103,1	0,0	0,0	0,0

On average, maintaining one goat requires 340-350 horse power per year. Goats cover up to 75-80% of their annual needs through pasture feeds, while the remaining 20-25% are obtained as supplementary feed during non-pasture days, and in their absence, they are forced to use the body's reserves. Therefore, during prolonged winters, animals lose significantly in their live weight, and very often die if they are not given additional feed.

The production of livestock products is mainly determined by the type, number of breeding animals, their heredity, health status, and the level of their feeding.

Discussion. A confident and continuous increase in livestock production can only be achieved by creating highly productive breeding herds. The health and productivity of agricultural animals are factors determining the profitability of the industry and their manifestation largely depend on the composition and completeness of the rations, the quality of the feed used, and the conditions created for animals throughout the year. Goats in Karakalpakstan are bred in all districts. They are unpretentious, well-adapted, and fertile.

A sharp snout, thin and very mobile lips allow the goats to eat small and low-growing grass, and to utilize shrubs, stubble, and branched fodder well. In sparse pastures with low grass, where cattle, horses, and even sheep remain hungry, goats find enough fodder and do not reduce their productivity. The unique biological characteristics of goats contribute to their successful breeding in areas with sparse herbaceous and shrub vegetation.

In Karakalpakstan, goats are mainly raised for meat production. Goat meat has been consumed since ancient times and is not inferior to lamb in terms of quality. The meat and fat yield of goats after slaughter, depending on the sex, fatness, and age of the animal, ranges from 35.0 to 50.0%. The best meat is obtained from young animals and castrates. In addition to meat, local goats produce coarse wool (0.5-1.5 kg), goat pelts (goat skins), and other products. Proper and rational production and use of goat products contribute to increasing the profitability of the industry and, accordingly, improving the living standards of local livestock breeders.

Conclusion. Therefore, to further increase the number of goats, increase their productivity, and improve the quality of products produced in Karakalpakstan, it is necessary:

- allocate preferential credit resources to increase the number of goats in farms and households;
- create the necessary conditions for feeding and maintenance, allocating the necessary number of pastures, water sources for long-term lease;
- systematically analyze the condition of pastures, apply rational systems for their use that exclude their degradation;
- establish systematic monitoring of the production of products in accordance with market requirements;
- in the context of the republic, designate regions for the preservation of local goats and districts for the creation of wool-producing, downy, and milk-producing goats;
- to carry out treatment and preventive measures in a timely manner;
- to create small enterprises, organize home-based work on the processing of goat products;
- organize exhibitions, demonstrations of best practices, and seminars to train farmers in advanced innovative technologies for producing and processing goat products.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННАЯ ЛИТЕРАТУРА

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